

Canine Impaction - Etiology - A Review Article

Sumita Biswas¹, Mridul Khanduri², Anita Bishnoi³, Varun Kashyap⁴

Received on: 05 October 2024; Accepted on: 19 November 2024; Published on : 14 December 2024

Post Graduate Student¹
Orthodontic, Dentofacial & Orthopaedic
Uttranchal Dental &
Medical Research Institute
Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Professor & HOD²
Orthodontic, Dentofacial & Orthopaedic
Uttranchal Dental &
Medical Research Institute
Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Senior Lecturer³
Orthodontic, Dentofacial & Orthopaedic
Uttranchal Dental &
Medical Research Institute
Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Reader⁴
Orthodontic, Dentofacial & Orthopaedic
Uttranchal Dental &
Medical Research Institute
Dehradun, Uttarakhand

Introduction

In terms of occlusion and aesthetics, permanent canines play a crucial role, and having an ideal canine-guided occlusion promotes and maintains a healthy temporomandibular joint and good functional mastication.¹

The canine-protected lateral function of the mandible facilitates contact and protects the remaining dentition from occlusal torsional masticatory forces during centric relation and centric occlusal functions.² It has been well established that tooth agenesis or absence or impaction affects a person's appearance, masticatory functions, and speech development causing emotional distress during young adulthood. In addition, it causes periodontal disease, dental mal position, and delayed development of the mandibular and maxillary bones.³ After the third molars, the maxillary canines are reported to be the most frequent tooth to be impacted, with an estimated prevalence of 1.7%, as stated by Ericson and Kuroi.⁴ Several etiological factors that have been proposed for the impaction of canines include long eruption times and genetic influences as the leading causes, apart from local and systemic causes.⁵ A previous study where a survey of different populations in their respective geographical area was conducted reported anomalous lateral incisors and palatal displaced canines at a similar frequency. The upper lateral incisor is typically used as a marker for canine impaction. Problems such as congenital absence, small size, peg shape, and ectopic position of this tooth are associated with maxillary canine impaction.⁶

Chronologically, the maxillary canine tooth germ develops before the first premolar tooth germ.⁷ Further clinical and radiographic analyses can facilitate early diagnosis of this condition. Prolonged retention of deciduous canines may be one of the earliest indications of canine impaction in the future. Therefore, it is necessary

to identify canine impaction early to implement an appropriate and effective orthodontic treatment plan.⁸

Etiology

While the exact etiology of the unerupted impacted maxillary canine remains somewhat elusive, there is strong evidence to suggest that several local factors—such as 1) Tooth size–arch length discrepancies; 2) failure of the primary canine root to resorb; 3) prolonged retention or early loss of the primary cuspid; 4) ankylosis of the permanent cuspid; 5) cyst or neoplasm; 6) dilacerated root; 7) absence of the maxillary lateral incisor and variation in root size of the lateral incisor (peg-shaped lateral incisor); and 8) variation in timing of lateral incisor root formation are thought to be important factors in canine impaction that involve several intricate and wide-ranging systems specifically, genetic, and systemic factors (such as diseases causing fever, endocrine problems, and/or radiation).⁹

Local Factors

1. Tooth Size–Arch Length Discrepancies

A. Discrepancy between tooth size and total arch length typically results in permanent teeth being unable to erupt into their proper positions in the dental arches. The teeth that erupt later in the series are impacted or deviate from their typical eruption routes when such discord is present.¹⁰

2. Failure of the Primary Canine Root to Resorb

Resorption of deciduous tooth roots is an advantageous procedure for the eruption of permanent dentition. Resorption usually occurs solely on the root

Access this article online

Website : www.healtalk.in

Quick Response Code

How to cite this article - Biswas et al. : Canine Impaction - Etiology - A Review Article
HTAJOCD 2024

of the primary canine when a upper permanent cuspid emerges apical to a permanent lateral incisor and a primary cuspid. Variations in the content and structure of permanent and primary roots may cause unequal resorption. Or perhaps the surfaces of primary and permanent roots have distinct kinds of extracellular matrix proteins that control and begin odontoclast adhesion. Odontoclast receptors for integrin may be the mediators of this attachment, and they may then influence retrieval action.¹¹ The mechanism of the root resorption is shown in fig-1.¹²

Fig-1 Representative scheme of RANK/RANKL/OPG system in the activation and inactivation of odontoclasts adapted from Tyrovola et al. in 2008

Lappin¹³ observed that deciduous canines were usually over-retained, having lengthy and unresorbed roots (Fig. 2). He suggested that the abnormality was caused by non-resorption of the deciduous canine. The author did not conduct a controlled study and relied exclusively on his observations to conclude. Root resorption of primary canine happens when the dental follicle is close to an unerupted permanent tooth, however its precise process is uncertain.

Fig-2 Panoramic view of a 12-year-old girl with a palatally impacted maxillary left canine. An enlarged dental follicle surrounds its crown (yellow arrows), and the deciduous canine has a long unresorbed root (white arrows).

The unresorbed root of the primary cuspid may not be the reason for shifting, instead it's the outcome of it.

3. Prolonged retention or early loss of the primary cuspid

The Physical impediment of a permanent canine emergence into the oral cavity is mainly determined by the retention of deciduous canines and their resistance to timely exfoliation.¹⁴

Many authors also have assessed root resorption in these cases; first was the absence of physiologic root resorption of primary canines, as ectopically positioned permanent canines typically do not cause resorption of the primary canine roots. Moreover, it could be due to the altered path of the canine, which could cause retention.¹⁵

Fig-3 An Impacted Canine Due to the Presence of a Deciduous Canine

In a study by Thilander et. al.¹⁶, most of the remaining deciduous teeth had canines in the dental arch during the fourth inspection. The previous examination only affected two of these; the others were positioned in the palatally. Consequently, it makes sense to conclude that the existence of permanent deciduous canine results from impaction rather than from its causation.

4. Ankylosis of The Permanent Cuspid

Tooth ankylosis is a common cause of dental trauma, affecting 6% of the population. It occurs in 29.5% of adult patients in their fourth decade, with failure to erupt due to tooth ankylosis to the surrounding bone or replacement resorption. It can also occur secondary to orthodontic treatment of specific impacted teeth. Possible explanations include etchant leakage during surgical exposure, mechanical damage, or tooth tilting while bonding and exposure procedure respectively, but the etiology is unclear and further research is needed.

Ankylosis secondary retention is linked to local viral infection by a varicella-zoster virus, with genetic and epigenetic factors potentially initiating the process in the periodontal ligament.¹⁷

5. Cyst or Neoplasm

Over retained deciduous canines often become nonvital by 12 years due to caries, trauma, or attrition, resulting in a chronic periapical granuloma, which can deflect or arrest the canine's eruption.

Figure 4- Impacted Canine Due to Large Follicle and Cyst Formation

Granulomas can develop into radicular cysts by stimulating Malassez, which would displace unerupted teeth, or cause cystic changes in the follicular sac of the adjacent unerupted permanent canine, causing benign enlargement and eventual dentigerous cyst formation. Hydrostatic pressure in a cyst prevents tooth eruption, causing tooth backup. The cyst may enlarge by resorbing adjacent bone until it contacts adjacent teeth's roots, displacing them into resorbable bone.¹⁸

7. Absence And Peg-shape Of The Maxillary Lateral Incisor

Liuk W. I. et al.¹⁹ suggested that the position of palatally displaced canines were associated with a change in the size and angulation of maxillary lateral incisors. This may be due to racial differences in jaw bone structure between European and Asian populations. The frequency of resorption of lateral incisors was seen to be increased when the impacted maxillary canines approached the midpalate line.

Figure 5 Impacted Canine in Peg-shaped Lateral

Several authors have proposed a guidance theory that explains the palatal displacement of maxillary canines due to the absence of guidance from a malformed or missing lateral incisor.^{20,21}

The lateral incisor root is still theorized to guide the path of maxillary canine eruption. Any root formation disruption in the shape and size of the lateral incisor may lead to canine impaction.²⁰ The agenesis or absence of lateral incisor may also result in impaction of the canine.^{6,21}

8. Variation in the Timing of Lateral Incisor Root Formation.

It has been noted that Small teeth erupt late, affecting the variable upper lateral incisor more than the stable cuspid.

Delays in lateral incisor development can lead to insufficient development for critical guidance in early cuspid migration stages.

The development of slow-forming lateral incisors can impede the cuspid's correct buccal migration, suggesting investigation of potential palatal displacement in all cases of anomalous incisors.²³

9. Hormonal Factors

Researchers for this anomaly attribute hormonal disturbances and systemic causes.²² Estimation of T3, T4, and TSH is required for diagnosing hypothyroidism with low serum T4 and elevated TSH. The

Evaluation of total serum calcium concentration and serum parathyroid hormone are necessary for this investigation of pseudohypo-parathyroidism. In both conditions, the level of serum calcium decreases. There is an increase of parathyroid hormone in pseudohypoparathyroidism and a decrease of hormones in hypoparathyroidism. Impacted teeth are also associated with Vitamin D deficiency and rickets.²⁴

Conclusion

The preventive strategy includes early detection of maxillary permanent canine ectopic eruption. In terms of both appearance and functionality, the management of the impacted canines is crucial. Clinicians must create patient-centred treatment plans and be well-versed in diverse treatment options. Clinicians can lessen the occurrence of ectopic eruption and the ensuing impaction of the maxillary canine by properly evaluating and treating their patients. As long as there is adequate space for permanent canines to erupt into the dental arch in an upright position, this technique allows them to do so. Adequate surgical methods and regulated force application are necessary for the proper management of impacted canines. Careful orthodontic technique selection is also crucial to provide effective correction and prevent damage to neighbouring teeth.

References

1. Thakur H. et al. Surgical exposure of a unilateral impacted mandibular canine followed by orthodontic extrusion: a case report. *Journal of South Asian Association of Pediatric Dentistry*. 2018;22-6.
2. Pasricha N. et al. Canine-protected occlusion. *Indian Journal of Oral Sciences*. 2012;3(1):13-8
3. Kambalimath V. H. et al. Permanent Maxillary Canine Agenesis: A Rare Case Report. *International Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*. 2015;8(3):242-6.
4. Ericson S. and Kurol J. Longitudinal study and analysis of clinical supervision of maxillary canine eruption. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol*. 1986;14:112-6.
5. Bass TB. Observations on the misplaced upper canine tooth. *Dent Pract Dent Rec*. 1967;18:25-33.
6. Brin I. et al. Position of the maxillary permanent canine in relation to anomalous or missing lateral incisors: a population study. *European Journal of Orthodontics*. 1986;8:12-6.
7. Archer W. H. *Text book of oral and maxillofacial surgery* WBSaunders Company, Philadelphia, USA. 1985.
8. Mew J. et al. Canine impaction: How effective is early prevention? An audit of treated cases. *Stoma Edu J*. 2015;2(2):114-9.
9. Hamada Y. et al. Canine impaction – A review of the prevalence, etiol-

- ogy, diagnosis, and treatment. *Seminars in Orthodontics*. 2019; 25(2):117-23.
10. McBride L. J: Traction-A surgical/orthodontic procedure. *AM. J. ORTHOD.* 1979;73: 287-99.
 11. Davies et al. Deciduous canine and permanent lateral incisor differential root resorption. *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 120(4), 339-347.
 12. Tyrovola JB, Spyropoulos MN, Makou M, Perrea D. Root resorption and the OPG/RANKL/RANK system: a mini-review. *J Oral Sci* 2008; 50(4):367-76.
 13. Lappin MM. Practical management of the impacted maxillary canine. *Am J Orthod* 1951;37:769-78.
 14. Litsas G. A review of early displaced maxillary canines: aetiology, diagnosis and interceptive treatment. *Open Dent J*. 2011;5(1):39-47.
 15. Kettle M. A. Treatment of the unerupted maxillary canine. *Trans Br Soc Orthod.* 1957; 32:74-84.
 16. Thilander et al. (1968). Local factors in impaction of maxillary canines. *Acta Odontologica Scandinavica*. 1968;26(1-2):145-68.
 17. Hadi A. et al. Ankylosed permanent teeth: incidence, etiology and guidelines for clinical management. *Med Dent Res*, 2018;1(1): 1-11.
 18. Beckera A. and Chaushu S. Etiology of maxillary canine impaction: A review. *Ajodo*.2015;148(4);557-67.
 19. Liuk W. I. et al. Associations between palatally displaced canines and maxillary lateral incisors. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2013;143(5):622-32.
 20. Ericson S. and Kuro J. Radiographic assessment of maxillary canine eruption in children with clinical signs of eruption disturbance. *Eur J Orthod.* 1986;8(3):133- 40.
 21. Yilmaz H. et al. Impacted maxillary canines and their relationship with lateral incisor resorption: a cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) study. *Australasian Orthodontic Journal.* 2020;36(2):160-7.
 22. Agarwal N. et al. A Rare Case Report of Multiple Over-retained Deciduous Teeth. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research.* 2023;17(11):6-8.
 23. Scott, J. H. and Symons, N. B. B.: *Introduction to dental anatomy*. E. & S. Living-stone. Ltd. Edinburgh and London, 1974 Ed.;7th edition: p. 13-5.
 24. Jahanimoghadam F. and Hosseinifar R. Case Report: Simultaneous Presence of Primary and Permanent Teeth. *Anatomical Sciences.* 2015;12(3):145-7.

Your Paper
was widely

PUBLISHED

will be read of the approximately

50,000 DENTISTS

through our Platforms

Publish your work for wide readership

+91 90 27 637 477
+91 1342 359 420

www.updent.in
www.healtalk.in